

PRODOMEA

PROject on high compatibility technologies and systems for conservation and
Documentation of masonry works in archaeological sites in the MEditerranean Area
Contract No ICA3-CT-2002-10021

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Confirming the International Role of community Research
INCO : International Scientific Cooperation Projects (1998-2002)

Introduction :

PRODOMEA is a PROject on high compatibility technologies and systems for conservation and DOcumentation of masonry works in archaeological sites in the MEditerranean Area

The Prodomea project comes within the framework of the INCO Programme (FP5 – INCO – Med – ICA3-CT-2002-10021) with the intention of developing the theme of **compatibility of conservation actions on archaeological masonry** and opening this concept not only to strictly physical parameters but also to operational and local context considerations.

The problem to be solved and investigated is the frequently observed bad satisfactory behaviour of the past conservation treatments in sites located all around the Mediterranean area. The main focus of the project is on archaeological mortars and their conservation treatments.

Ancient construction technologies in the Mediterranean basin present significant similarities, due chiefly to natural, climatic and meteorological conditions common to the entire area and also to the intense flow of trade and contacts between the area's different civilisations that have contributed to bring those technologies still closer together. The protection and conservation of the construction heritage have diffused the techniques evolved in masonry construction over the entire area in various periods and dominations. In many cases the effects of these actions have proved to be unsatisfactory, in particular as regards the quality of the conservation action over time. So the first objective of the Prodomea project has been *to study these actions through several sampling campaigns and tests* carried out in all the archaeological sites of the project. Two *analytical methodologies* were applied in order to characterize both the archaeological / original materials and the materials used in the past conservation actions, as well as to describe the environmental effects acting on them. This has meant not only studying 'modern' technologies, but also "rediscovering" ancient and traditional treatments and their way of working, analyzing them in order to compare their results in different contexts.

In fact the second objective was to try to transform existing and scattered conservation strategies on archaeological masonry into a more friendly, structured and sustainable one. The result has been the definition of a *new approach for assessment of the compatibility of conservation treatments* on masonry architectural assets present in archaeological sites in the Mediterranean basin and to transform it an a useful *IT tool* in order to better exchange and manage the knowledge *on compatibility and conservation treatments*.

These outcomes were possible because Prodomea has promoted a consortium of partners and supported them into a network to behave as a flexible, virtual organisation that has exchanged and structured the collected data.

The Compatibility Approach

The building up of a road towards a Compatibility approach in Heritage Conservation for mortars restoration required the exploration of many issues and it had to include the development of proper methodologies and tools to assess how each action is far from being fully compatible.

The *Compatibility Approach* provides support for selecting appropriate methodologies (strategies) and tools (tasks) to introduce compatibility in the conservation process and to *assess the incompatibility level* as part of an integrated conservation planning for mortars restoration.

When addressing the concept of Compatibility and its meaning, the team assumed that in general conservation interventions, even in archaeological sites, carry a certain level of risk and that it is neither technically nor economically feasible to advise that only interventions without risk should be acceptable. Therefore, the ultimate achievable aim is certainly *not to find "perfectly compatible" actions, but to find those that minimise the degree of incompatibility*.

The Compatibility Approach of the project has been defined as a “guiding concept” in masonry mortars’ conservation to support technical management and to turn the interventions more effective and sustainable.

The decision on the Compatibility Approach for the PRODOMEA project is strictly based on providing an instrument in which the guiding concepts for analysis of the action are the criteria of technical, operational, environmental, social and cultural compatibility.

PRODOMEA team decided to characterize the *Incompatibility concept* by establishing a clear framework of criteria in order to facilitate the integration and the assessment of compatibility into the conservation process. By suggesting a set of parameters/indicators to frame the *(In)Compatibility concept* its non unique and provisional nature shall be underlined. In fact the structure / listing of items should be seen as a first tool for ordering and organizing knowledge, also stressing that its improvement should remain as an objective in continuous progress.

The final performance of a given conservation intervention is influenced by a large set of factors, components and constraints, either when they are explicitly considered or when simply ignored. This set of factors can be grouped in a “compatibility tree” where the major branches are the physical content, the environment factors, the operational background and the socio-cultural context that are subsequently subdivided in secondary branches, the basic components designated as “compatibility indicators”.

In a short description, the first order **branches** can be defined as follows:

- i) the **physical content** represents the characteristics of the materials and include the intrinsic properties responsible for the effective performance of the intervention action, considered in its material side;
- iii) the **operational background** includes all the possible factors of an immaterial nature (availability of tools, practices and constraints) that influence the quality of the conservation intervention through their interference in the decision makers, planners and operators;
- iv) the **socio-cultural context** includes all the social components associated to any conservation intervention that, although having no direct impact in the material incompatibility, are relevant for facilitating the acceptance of the conservation intervention by the local communities and may play a significant role in the final quality of the intervention.

Considering that the interaction between the conservation materials and the archaeological materials depend on the external factors, an assessment of the **environmental constraints** is also considered.

The major challenge in the assessment of compatibility is to be able to define a precise methodology to integrate the information that is provided by each individual Compatibility Indicator (CI) and to prepare the way to reach a quantified overall value for the degree of Incompatibility.

The Compatibility Indicators (CIs) are the basic elements of Incompatibility and are assumed to be quantifiable in terms of their potential influence in the overall incompatibility. Any CI should contain

relevant information, but inevitably it is only a partial component of the overall compatibility. Therefore the CIs should not be interpreted isolated or out of context, since this may lead to erroneous conclusions and misinterpretations.

Each individual CI has a role in the final assessment of compatibility and in principle it can be assumed that it is possible to rate its importance according to the relative role that it plays in terms of Incompatibility.

In order to make it possible to integrate the different parameters in the overall assessment of compatibility and to give each parameter the role that it effectively has in the final Incompatibility it was necessary to create a system of translating the diverse quantifying units or descriptive terms into a uniform system that would allow the integration of components that constitute an intrinsically inhomogeneous set.

The translation tool is called the **rating system** and it consists of qualifying the position of a given action in a rational graduation between 0 and 10, for each Compatibility Indicator, according to its potential as inducer of negative (harmful) effects for the conservation objectives. In other terms, the ratings given to each CI indicate how the assessed action is positioned in terms of higher or lower degree of incompatibility. The rules suggested for the rating process are a first approach to the problem and although some of them found some supported in personal research data or in the available literature, some others are just based on logical and comparative reasoning. This means that further research is required to validate and calibrate the system in order to properly build up a reliable and strongly supported methodology.

Once a suitable system of ratings is conceived and properly defined (be it the present one or any other), there is the expectancy that it will possible to integrate the identified indicators in a quantifiable unified assessment. This quantifiable assessment is translated as an incompatibility degree.

For some typical situations, tables containing relevant indicators and the respective rating were prepared. By treating those ratings with appropriate mathematical formulations it is possible to compute the overall incompatibility degree of any given conservation operation or to specifically assess the local (specific) incompatibility of a conservation treatment. In specific circumstances it may also be of interest to use it as a checklist for finding the less harmful alternatives of any given conservation action.

Different computing formulas can be applied and only the real practice will prove which are the meaningful and operative ones.

In one of such expressions, the **Incompatibility Degree (ID)** is computed as the quadratic mean of the indicators, as follows.

$$ID_n = \sqrt{\frac{P_1^2 + P_2^2 + \dots + P_n^2}{n}}$$

Where:

ID_n = is the incompatibility degree,

P₁ ... P_n = are the ratings of the relevant indicators,

n = is the number of indicators used in the computation of **ID_n**

With the scale from 0 to 10 and the computation formulas given above, **ID_n** has the following meaning:

ID_n = 0 characterises a perfect, compatible action

ID_n = 10 characterises a fully incompatible one

The significance of **ID_n** in its overall meaning can be directly taken from its position in the scale 0 to 10. However, it is important to stress that important benefits can arise from the analysis of the individual values given to some specific indicators, namely to those eventually considered as critical ones. It will be a good practice, too, to revisit the indicators that have received ratings in the upper third part of the scale (8-10) and discuss the impact of those indicators and, eventually, to seek for adequate measures to deal with the expected consequences of such high ratings.

This theoretical background is the support for the definition and building up of a Decision Support System that will constitute an important IT Tool at the service of the conservation practitioners.

To our knowledge this use of *quantifiable indicators* for defining the Incompatibility level of conservation actions constitutes a ***real novel (innovative) methodology in Cultural Heritage***.

The Prodomea IT tool

Prodomea IT tool has been developed for selecting appropriate methodologies and tools to introduce compatibility in the conservation process and to assess the InCompatibility level as part of an integrated conservation planning.

The Prodomea IT tool can be reached through internet at Prodomea web site (www.Prodomea.com) and allows you to use the IT Tool in several ways:

Knowledge Base: it contains the different groups of documentation that constitutes the knowledge base of the Prodomea project, above all in particular about Compatibility and Conservation of archaeological mortars. The main section of KB is dedicated to *Materials and Techniques*. It constitutes the knowledge base with which the DSS interacts when applying the compatibility evaluation procedure. It contains, as basic reference data, the data coming from the case study sites of the Prodomea project. *Literature* is another section of KB. It constitutes a sort of digital library., also if it is not built up as a real database, but it can be seen as an archive, subdivided in thematic categories where finding interesting and detailed documentation about new methods of testing or experimental conservation procedures studied inside Prodomea project or in other European projects. *DSS short reports*, finally, is a sort of “box” where a part of the results of full application of the DSS are, dynamically, stored with all the Prodomea case studies.

Case- studies: it is a presentation of the conservation actions that were analyzed and evaluated from the Compatibility point of view in the Prodomea archaeological sites. It allows to study the past treatments, as well as some new interventions, and analyse their ‘incompatibility rating’ in order to identify and describe several case studies of masonry treatment that can be seen as “best or bad practice”, also in terms of technologies and materials, but also from the point of view of sustainability.

DSS– Prodomea decision support system: this is a tool to apply the new Prodomea approach for the assessment of the level of incompatibility of conservation treatments on masonry architectural assets present in archaeological sites. The Prodomea-dss aims at being an helpful instruments for :

- ***evaluating the Incompatibility Degree of past interventions***. InCompatibility assessment in past interventions is the procedure that scientists, conservators and restorers could use to evaluate the past interventions. This procedure can be applied as a “control tool” in order to identify and evaluate best and bad practice.

- **choosing the less Incompatible intervention processes**, or the best intervention concept, or the more appropriate actions in new Intervention. This part of DSS is structured as a procedure aiming at helping the different key-actors of the conservation process to understand where they can meet problems linked to Compatibility when preparing their conservation plan, when defining the conservation concept or when designing the conservation actions. The Prodomea team has identified 8 key-phases, each of them containing a list of recommended actions and check-list.

Evaluating the Incompatibility Degree of past interventions

In-Compatibility assessment in past interventions is the procedure that scientists, conservators and restorers could use to evaluate the Incompatibility Degree of past interventions.

This procedure can be applied as a “control tool” on past intervention in order to identify and evaluate best and bad practices. But the bad satisfactory effect of the past conservation treatments, and in general the final performance of the conservation intervention, can be related to several aspects that occur during the conservation intervention, for example:

- the application of non compatible / suitable treatments
- non consideration of the environmental stress & factors
- lack of skills of the operators
- lack of control during the interventions
-

For understanding the causes of a poor level treatment or of a highly performing action we have to investigate different aspects of the intervention. The DSS requires that some important steps be followed:

- 1) first of all it is necessary to identify the site and the monument. Several information can be stored here but it is suggested to insert, at least:
 - a. the name of the site and of the monument that you are analysing,
 - b. the description of the decay state of the monument and of the treatment that you would like to assess,
- 2) the initial evaluation that must be carried out involves the environmental aspects of the site: the environmental assessment. It is necessary step, in order to have the constraints of the environment around the site that could help explaining some of the decay processes described in the previous step.

The following steps of the assessment of past interventions have been structured in two levels referring to two main phases of the conservation process that take into consideration the different aspects mentioned above.

- 3) the upper level of the conservation process, in which the evaluation refers to the conservation concept in order to confront its conceptual visions with the general wide context of its practical application. The parameters involved are those referred to Operational Background and Socio-Cultural Context. They measure the interactions of the planned actions with the surrounding context and take into account the relationships between them;
- 4) the technological level of the conservation intervention, in which the assessment refers mainly to the physical and technical characteristics of the materials, the environmental constraints and the operational parameters strictly linked to the chosen conservation technologies.

The procedure of assessment of the Physical-Chemical component was studied for assessing the compatibility of composite masonry (masonry made of relevant proportions of mortar and stone and/or brick) and assumes that users are able to identify the weakest combination.

Choosing the less Incompatible intervention processes

The new Intervention DSS is structured as a procedure aiming at helping the different key-actors of the conservation process to choose the less Incompatible intervention processes, the best intervention concept or the more appropriate intervention actions. Or, in a better way, it will help these key-actors to understand where they can meet problems linked to Incompatibility when preparing their conservation plan, when defining the conservation concept or when designing the conservation actions. We could identify **8 key-phases¹**, each of them containing a *list of recommended actions* that, in the experience of the Prodomea Team, are fundamental for the remedy of masonry damage and for reaching a high compatible and sustainable level in the conservation of the concerned monument.

The IT Tool procedure provides:

- a check list for the preparation of the phase of the interventions for each ‘Prodomea step’, that the key-actors could follow in order to prepare a ‘more qualified’ conservation plan,
- sub-routines for the evaluation of the level of ‘Incompatibility’ of some activities that the key-actors are planning, giving them the idea on ‘how (in)compatible’ is the action that they are undertaking. Or better, what kinds of problems they will eventually meet.

The inclusion of this kind of ‘sub-routines’ for the evaluation of the Incompatibility Degree of the actions previewed in each phase may certainly be an interesting use of the system. In this assumption, the system can be seen as a “design tool” to support end-users in defining the less Incompatible conservation plan or conservation actions.

¹ In order to highlight these potential uses, we took as a starting document the 15 steps defined for Petra as a standard procedure or guide for the conservation interventions- [link to the document of Petra](#)

The 8 key-phases are briefly described here below:

STEP A – Pre-diagnostic

The prediagnostic phase includes a component of investigation that, in medical terms, corresponds to what is normally called anamnesis and it includes a first survey of the degradation forms and of the distinctive materials. The aim of this step is to identify the monument, its history and architectural significance and to have a first picture of its state of the damage, in order to be able to correctly address the following phases of diagnosis and intervention.

STEP B – Diagnostic phase (or Diagnosis)

The diagnosis uses the information provided by the pre-diagnostic phase and complements it with new data and additional reasoning in order to build up a scientific support for the definition and implementation of compatible conservation measures. The first aim of the diagnosis is the identification of the damage causes and of the interpretation of the decay processes active on site. In the sequence, it aims at selecting the solutions for the identified problems, namely by acting as far as possible directly on the identified causes. For reaching these aims, on site and lab studies may be required, namely for the characterisation of materials and decay products, for the quantification of decay rates and for the interpretation of the masonry and mortar damage processes.

STEP C – Conservation concept

The main aim of this phase is the construction of a theoretical and ethical framework under which the practical conservation actions should be selected and deployed. It should include a precise identification of what is to be conserved, the indication of the major conservation actions needed, the identification of the acceptable procedures (and of the non-acceptable, if critical) and the limits for the intervention. The really relevant issues expected from this conservation concept phase are not the written documents but the identification of the processes that should be used to truly evaluate the appropriateness of a specific conservation intervention (involving local stakeholders and the scientific community) and whether and how it can be implemented. The goal of this step is to provide a basic framework of information necessary to determine if the conservation intervention should be initiated and how and to monitor its subsequent implementation phase.

STEP D – Intervention actions

This step uses the information provided by the diagnostic phase and, on the basis of the decision taken in the Conservation Concept phase, provides the scientific and technological background for the definition of compatible conservation measures. The overall aim of the phase is the preparation of a complete framework that will contain the basic information to be transmitted to the conservation-restoration team concerning the execution of the conservation actions.

STEP E – Intervention plan

In programming a restoration intervention it is fundamental to have an efficacious tool for arranging the intervention “working chains” and in this way to check the consequentiality and mutual implications of all intervention phases, from the project desk to the work site. Of particular relevance are the precise identification and scaling of the intervention actions, the establishment of minimum requirements for the operational team, the estimation of costs and the anticipation of the critical issues that might reasonably be expected.

STEP F – Selection of operators

The selection of operators is the turning point from the research and planning steps to the execution and implementation phase. A bad or improper selection may jeopardise an entire process, even those that have fulfilled the previous phases with high standards. The selection shall address the team composition (academic background, practical experience, distribution of responsibilities) as well as the comprehensiveness of the work proposal, the working phasing and also the eventual restrictions or modifications raised or suggested by the applicants about the tender work programme. Although in a different level, the criteria adopted in the selection process also play a decisive role, and all the selection procedures that use the proposal cost as the major selection criterion may lead to the selection of inappropriate candidates and to overall unsatisfactory interventions.

STEP G – Intervention execution plan

The executive intervention plan is a critical moment in a restoration/conservation intervention. It shall take into account the information gathered during the previous research and survey phases in order to produce detailed work instructions for the site team. In reality, the executive phase in a restoration intervention is a decisive step, since any mistakes made in this phase may jeopardise all the good intentions, plans and studies carried out in the precedent phases.

In this context, the contractor, as a key-player of this step, shall define precise methodologies for the different types of tasks to be carried out and shall submit them to the appreciation and approval of the responsible/designer of the intervention. Given the importance of the decisions expected to be taken in this step, it is also important that the project designer works closely with the site manager (when corresponding to two distinct entities) in order to ensure constant consequentiality between forecasts and the work performed.

STEP H – Intervention Execution – Intervention Control

The execution phase is the final step of the conservation intervention. A good or bad result is “materialised” in this phase. It is the time when operators have the “hands on” with all the consequences that can be easily anticipated. The operators and their supervisors must respect the plans and directives defined in the previous steps, although considering that even the best plan may accept improvements. The operators must show high availability to interact with the site responsible, namely whenever any modification or improvement is considered possible or desirable. The site responsible must deploy a strict supervising scheme with permanent control over the technical and logistic aspects of the works and should never delegate in the contractor the ultimate capacity of deciding on any relevant modification to the work plan. The contractor must report all the actions carried out, the materials used, the procedures adopted and the final condition of the object achieved with the intervention works. It is also expected that the contractor complement the condition survey maps with the information gathered during the intervention works.....

The conservation technologies towards compatibility

The progress made by the PRODOMEA project in terms of the Compatibility concept leads to the conclusions that no specific technology per se, in absolute terms, should be attributed a quality of “compatible”. In other words, when attributing a numeric rating of incompatibility to each combination of ‘material’ in ‘socio-cultural context’ with ‘operational conditionings’ and under given ‘environmental constraints’ conditions, we are implicitly assuming that universal ideally compatible interventions do not exist.

However, the PRODOMEA project has studied and assessed a very significant number of *conservation technologies and archaeological materials*, whose descriptions and characterization is a very important component of the project outcomes (figure a, b, c). These technologies are fully described, with the related tests and incompatibility assessment results, in the PRODOMEA IT Tool, in the section devoted to Knowledge Base. They cover a large diversity of actions and some were assessed with the project tools. Although stressing that extrapolations may not be appropriate, the study of those results will certainly be of great interest for comparative purposes.

The character of being ‘traditional’ or ‘similar’ may help to reach more compatible solutions, but when alone they are not enough to guarantee compatibility. In fact these terms have very fuzzy meanings, not specifically envisaging compatibility issues and they may also vary in time and space. A traditional mortar can be prepared by many different processes and have varied physical and mechanical properties. The behaviour of a “lime mortar” is not the same everywhere. Different operators prepare “traditional” mortars differently and apply them in their own way. A repair mortar may seem to be similar to the substratum mortar, but were the effects of the degradation processes taken into account?

The cultural context and the operational conditionings have relevant influence in the overall compatibility of a given conservation action and they should not be considered as irrelevant. By disregarding these immaterial components may bring about very negative consequences. They may include political and administrative reasons and both can be in the origin of inappropriate conservation practice. The sudden availability of some amount of money to be applied in a specific monument may “oblige” the site manager to proceed rapidly to the intervention phase with insufficient diagnostic and even lack of information in critical aspects. The consequences of such procedure may be very detrimental for the adequate preservation of the monument.

Similar consequences may result from the application of administrative rules that were not specifically drawn having in mind the activity of monument’s conservation. Simple questions such as the accreditation of operators (for instance by requiring a too high economic background for the registering process) and the selection procedures (for instance by giving to the cost an excessive weight in the selection process) may completely jeopardise an entire conservation intervention. The precise definition of the conservation objectives to be reached, the requirement of well-prepared conservation teams (with demonstrated results and with obligation to engage in the site the persons indicated in the tender documents) as well as the attribution of the highest weight to the technical quality of the proposal are the antidotes at reach when such drawbacks are identified and wished to be overcome.

Automatic and acritic adoption of foreign ‘compatible’ technologies is risky and should be avoided. When going through the PRODOMEA supporting documents it is easily seen that the local conditions play a decisive role in the Incompatibility degree and therefore it is obvious that any technology has to be screened at the light of the local conditions before being adopted. The critical assessment provided by the PRODOMEA approach is considered as a relevant instrument for proper adaptation of such technologies

figure a

figure b

The archaeological sites

For each site:

two pages to describe the site, the samples campaign, the plan of conservation (past) analysed, the fieldwork work / action carried out, the result of the assessment carried out. Please attach photos and tables or figures to the description in word.

Responsibles:

Giannutri (I), ...**Paola Rendini & Roberto Sabelli**

Giannutri (I),

The island of Giannutri, close to that of Giglio, makes up the southern part of the Tuscan archipelago. Despite the inhospitality of the terrain with its calcareous soil, and the difficulty for anchoring vessels, the island has nevertheless served for centuries as an emergency haven, as testified by the frequent underwater finds. It also became home to one of the most splendid and complex Roman pleasure retreats, a true villa of otium of the Imperial Rome. The Villa Domizia of Giannutri on the island's west coast stretches inland to cover about four hectares. The villa is one of the best and most comprehensive examples of an "equipped" imperial residence. The complex still has its late Flavian feel, with its type of plan and decorations, although these have now almost entirely disappeared. It was built towards the end of the 1st century AD and a number of modifications were made at the beginning of the 2nd century. It consists of a series of nuclei that were used each for different purposes and constructed so as to be closely and attractively connected to the surrounding landscape.

In the framework of the Prodomea project two main conservation plans has been taken into account and analyzed in details through several samples campaign and the application of the Compatibility approach:

- a previous intervention carried out during the years 1999-2001, which results were studied in detail in the framework of the research project;
- a new intervention, that started on 2004 and that were monitored during the last year of research project.

Damascus (Syria), Talal Akili – Mouaffak Doughman

Damascus (Syria),

Jupiter Temple of Damascus - The temple reached its architectural zenith and expansion in the second and third centuries BC. It lies in the mid-western half of Old Damascus on a little hill overlooking the city, and was about 10 meters higher than the ground of the old city. The difference has disappeared nowadays by the rise of the ground level around the hill. The temple was surrounded with two walls, one surrounding the other. The first wall, the bigger and outermost one, is about 380 m long and 310m wide. It supported the arcade that shaded the shops below. The wall had two grand entrances: one to the east and the other to the west – their remnants are still there. The other wall, smaller and innermost, surrounds the Cella or the house of Gods. Its borders are the walls of the present Umayyad Mosque, which are 166 m long from east to west, and 96 m wide from north to south. Its construction was similar to the construction of the outer wall, and had a square tower on each corner. The outer walls of the temple have remained in their place since the 2nd century AD, and they have included the Jupiter Temple inside them, and afterwards they have included the Cathedral of John the Baptist and finally the Umayyad Mosque.

The initial list of techniques chosen for the Prodomea knowledge base comprises at the instance four traditional conservation treatments collected in the area of Damascus.

- **JOINTING MORTAR (filling for mortar joints)**
- **RENDERING MORTAR (traditional calcimine works)**
- **JOINTING MORTAR (Mortar of Joints and Stone Mounting)**
- **STONE REPAIR MORTAR (Mortar for Stone Restoration)**

**JUPITER TEMPLE,
Umayyad Mosque DAMACUS (SIRYA)**

Mekawer Fortress (J), Luigi Marino & Simona Carnevale

Mekawer Fortress (J)

The fortress owes its fame to the decapitation of John the Baptist ordered by Herod Antipas as according to the story recounted by Josephus. It is an important component of the vast system of fortifications of Herod the Great (37-4 BC) and strengthened by his descendants, that also included Machaerous, Jerusalem and Masada, Hyrcania, Alexandreion, Kypros, Herodium (the summer residence near Bethlehem that became his tomb) and another Herodium, east of the Jordan. Machaerous was founded by Alexander Ianneus (90 BC) as a Hasmonean strong point for defence against the Nabataeans of Petra. Destroyed by the Roman governor Gabinius (57 BC), it was reconstructed during the reign of Herod the Great. On his death, the fortress was included in the tetrarchy of Herod Antipas until it passed under the control of Agrippa (37 AD). During the Jewish revolt (66-74 AD) the fortress was one of the bulwarks against the Romans until its final destruction by Lucilius Bassus (72 AD). The investigations at the fortress covered the mortars used in the 1992-95 restoration work for consolidation, filling in of gaps and pick-up of masonry. These actions, in compliance with the concepts of compatibility, reversibility and minimum intervention, were carried out with lime and soil mortars. The aim of the investigations was to check on the reliability of the mortars used, with a view to deciding whether it would be possible to use them in future actions. The intervention carries out actually is with mortar as similar as the original mortars and it is made "with samples" on the stairway of tree walls and on the bottom basin. The interventions are from the traditional typologies of practice: maintenance of interconnection mortars and plasters (lime and earth mortars), interconnection mortars and plasters (lime and local stones), interconnection mortars and plasters (lime and ash), plastering mortars (various typologies).

MEKAWER FORTRESS (JORDAN)

Petra (J),

Petra was the Capital of the Nabataean Kingdom roughly from 400BC to 106AD when the Romans annexed it to their Empire. It lies in the South of Jordan in UTM zone 36N and is marked by a very rough terrain and beautiful sandstone geologic formations of the Precambrian and Ordovician age. The Nabataeans carved their monuments from the sandstone massif that bordered the central ravine of the city. The monuments of Petra are subject to serious weathering damage that made it necessary for the Jordanian authorities and researchers from universities to make extensive studies of the natural, anthropogenic, and climatic conditions that cause the deterioration of the facades. A project supported by the German Government (through GTZ) has tried to apply the latest technologies in conservation to try and slow down the process of damage at a number of monuments, namely rock-carved facades. Stone masonry structures are also found in Petra and they too are exposed to weathering problems. The problems in Petra are typical of general weathering and natural erosion affecting monuments. However, the presence of rock carved monuments directly in a natural habitat presents unique study cases that PRODOMEA tried to focus on.

In Petra the rock carved stone was the main focus. Monument 825 was studied as previous conservation treatment was applied to it. On the other hand field testing of Ordovician sandstone at The Djin Block No. 9. Modern mortar mixes and consolidants have been studied for the purpose of the project.

PETRA (JORDAN)

Troia (P).

Located at Tróia peninsula, in the Atlantic coast of Portugal, this archaeological site comprehends one of the most outstanding cases of known fish-salting industries of the Roman Empire. This fact motivated the attribution of National Monument category since nearly one hundred years ago by the Portuguese Government. Tróia was not the single one of this kind in the European Occident. In fact, this fish-salting industry was part of the complex trading chain centred in the Mediterranean sea (the Roman *Mare Nostrum*) that guaranteed the supply of a significant set of products to the imperial population centres. Built by the end of the first century before Christ, it was kept fully active until the middle of the third century after Christ. By that time, it began a progressive and irreversible decadence process until the fifth century AC as testified by the latest Roman vestiges found at the site. Tróia remains are still visible, ranging in an extension of almost two kilometres.

The dates and reports of the first archaeological surveys are not known. The earlier reference dates back to 1502, in a privilege attribution document issued by *Ordem de Santiago*, granting to a couple the land and its use near a lagoon for building tide mills. In the third quarter of the XVIII century the first archaeological excavation took place, by initiative of the future Queen D. Maria I. At the same time, further houses were discovered in the “Rua da Princesa”.

Based on recent past interventions, a previous evaluation study was made in order to assess the (in)compatibility of methodologies used on the last conservation plans implemented in Tróia site. Since the collected data were not very informative in terms of the elements available to support future interventions, a selection of technologies for future interventions was based in the analysis of the original Roman constructions with the purpose of matching the original solutions although incorporating some modern materials and technologies, that were tested on a second stage, on site.

The past and modern conservation technologies were tested using the Compatibility Approach (DSS).

TROIA, LISBONA (PORTUGAL)

**Confirming the International Role of community Research
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**MINISTERO
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LE ATTIVITÀ
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SBAT

Sovrintendenza per i Beni archeologici della Toscana

via della Pergola 65

50121 Firenze

Italy

**INSTITUTO
PORTUGUÊS DO
PATRIMÓNIO
ARQUITECTÓNICO**

IPP

Instituto português do Património Arquitectónico -Divisão de obras, conservação e restauro da Direção Regional de Lisboa, Palácio nacional de

Ajuda, Ala norte

1349-021 Lisboa

Portugal

HU

The Hashemite University

Queen Rania's Institute of Tourism and Heritage

The free zone Highway

13115 Zarqa

Jordan

ARCOD

ARCOD

University of Damascus

Faculty of Architecture

Architectural research centre of old Damascus

Maysaloun str.30

Damascus

Syria

ISAC-CNR

Consiglio nazionale delle Ricerche

Istituto di scienze dell'atmosfera e del clima

Via P. Gobetti 101

40129 Bologna

Italy

- ICIE Istituto Cooperativo per l'Innovazione (coordinator) -
- University of Florence, Department of the history of the architecture and restoration
- Soprintendenza per i Beni archeologici della Toscana
- IPPAR Instituto português do Património Arquitectónico Divisao de obras, conservacao e restauro da Direcao Regional de Lisboa
- Laboratorio Nacional de Engenharia Civil Building materials department
- The Hashemite University - Queen Rania's Institute of Tourism and Heritage
- ARCOD University of Damascus Faculty of Architecture - Architectural research centre of old Damascus
- ISAC-CNR Consiglio nazionale delle Ricerche - Institute for the atmosphere and climate sciences

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